

Colonial Political Economy of Iron Production and Technology in Nigeria: The Jos Plateau Case

Dimas Solomon Gubam^a Andrew Borok Maren^b

^aDepartment of Archaeology and Museum Studies, Federal University Lokoja, Nigeria.

^bDepartment of History and International Studies, Federal University Lokoja, Nigeria.

*Corresponding email: dimas.gubam@fulokoja.edu.ng

PAPER KEYWORDS

Colonial Economy,
Colonialism, Iron
Smelting, Revitalization.

ABSTRACT

Colonialism is a deliberate way of expressing the political might of the Europeans as well as a method of expanding markets for the industrial products, and an equally dumping ground for their waste products. In order to avoid competition, some policies were put in place to suppress any local industry (such as iron) that could pose a threat to their imported industrial products/waste in the colonies. The policies were enacted and enforced in such a manner that the local population would have no option but to depend on the imported materials/colonial economy. Both their political and economic policies were designed in such a way that the local economy was forced to collapse, but it was protected where it was to enhance their interests. This paper, therefore, focuses on the colonial economic policy in the Jos Plateau and how it impacted the local industries, particularly iron smelting. During World War II, an attempt was made to revive local iron-smelting industries (which they had destroyed through their economic policies) in the Jos-Plateau area to meet local needs and for export, since Europe was preoccupied with the war and was no longer producing iron. More so, iron was in high demand in Europe, and the only alternative for them was to revive the local iron smelting industries in the Jos-Plateau. The paper also discusses the colonial policies involved and other factors that contributed to the final collapse of the industry during the post-war period. Information for the writ-up was sourced from oral interviews, archival materials, textbooks, and journal articles. The paper concludes that the need to revive local iron-smelting industries in Jos-Plateau was prompted by the selfish colonial economic desires and not to benefit the interests of the people.

★ ★ ★

Received 14 May 2026
Revised 19 June 2026
Accepted 27 June 2026

This is an open-access article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. This permits unrestricted use and distribution in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited. ©2026 by the author..

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20996961>

Introduction

Jos Plateau is situated between latitudes 8° 30' and 10° 30' N, and longitudes 8° and 9° 30' E. The Jos Plateau has different geographical and climatic features that make it distinct from the immediate regions to the East, West, South, and North of it. It is a highland area with an average elevation of around 1,200 meters (3,937 feet) above sea level, covering an area of approximately 7,770 square kilometers (3,000 square miles). The Jos Plateau is bounded by the surrounding plains of the Bauchi and Taraba to the

East, Northern Kaduna to the north, Southern Kaduna to the west, and Nassarawa to the south (Borok and Gubam, 2021). The area is known for its unique geography, climate, and cultural heritage, with numerous ethnic groups, like Berom, Mwaghavul, Ngas, Afizere, Anaguta, Ngeomai, Pan, Tarok, and Ron, among others, thereby making it a unique area with so much archaeological potential due to a broadly linked cultural, economic, political, and linguistic past (Reid, 1994; Soper, 1971; Sutton, 1993). The geological formations consist basically of a Cambrian basement complex with granite rocks, which have cassiterite minerals, among which is tin. The plains of the area are dotted with laterite basalt flat-topped hills, which add to the scenic beauty of the Plateau (Morrison, 1977). The area is, however, dominated by the Chadic group of languages in the central and Southern parts, with a number of autochthonous groups in the north. Although no comprehensive archaeological work has been conducted on iron smelting in the Jos Plateau area, the famous Nok Iron Age, which flourished between 200 BC and 1000 AD, also covers part of the area (Bulus et al, 2001). Earlier investigations on iron smelting in the area have revealed that iron played a number of roles in various polities, ranging from functional, economic, ceremonial, ritual, cultural, and decorative to the symbolic maker of power and wealth.

The production processes of iron in the Jos Plateau societies followed the following processes: mining of ore, extracting iron from the ore, the blacksmithing process through which the impurities were finally removed from the bloom, iron implements forged by the blacksmith, and finally, distribution of the iron items. The entire process of iron production in the area was ritualized as it was a common belief that the ancestors and gods could make an exploration, a smelting, or a smithing exercise fruitless until some sacrifices were made to cleanse the land. It was the ancestors who could intercede on behalf of the people in the case of a fruitless smelt. The smelting and smithing of iron were accompanied by a variety of rules and taboos that must be observed, and failure to observe them can lead to an unsuccessful exercise. Smelting of iron, however, continued in the area until the mid-twentieth century, when some colonial policies were enforced against its production (Fwatshak, 2005).

Issues of origin

In archaeology, the Stone Age and the Iron Age are distinguished by the technologies they involve. Moreover, the presence of iron did not seem to bring about significant transformations in the lives of early humans. How the introduction of iron initially affected the people of Nigeria remains unclear, but it is clear that, despite its efficiency, early humans continued to use stone implements and iron tools concurrently for some time. However, it was not until Nigerian people from different regions acquired knowledge of iron smelting that an appreciable effect of the technology was observed in bush clearing and, subsequently, agriculture (Shaw, 1980). At some archaeological sites, evidence of transition from the Stone Age to the early Iron Age has been established (Fagg, 1959; York, 1965; Shaw, 1978), although the introduction of iron does not seem to mark a complete shift in cultural behavior, as many elements show continuity (Shaw, 1980).

It has been argued that the West African region has received more attention in archaeological and ethnographic research than other parts of Africa (Jemkur, 2004). A lot of data has been gathered on West African iron smelting (see Jemkur, 1985; Okafor,

1975a, 1975b; Tylecote, 1975a). The abundant raw materials for iron smelting in the region have been recognized by some scholars as possible factors that stimulated iron technology in the region (Lhote, 1952).

Issues concerning how the people of West Africa acquired the knowledge of iron smelting are surrounded by differing opinions. Scholars such as Mauny (1952), Williams (1969, 1974), Tylecote (1975), Schmidt and Avery (1983), and Phillipson (1985) argued in favour of the possible transfer of knowledge of iron smelting to Sub-Saharan Africa from Asia via Egypt and Meroe, or via Carthage. This argument rests on the assumption that Africa was a “Dark continent” with no idea of development (Lane, 2005; Andah, 1981). Africa was perceived as still battling behind Europe in all spheres of life (Holl, 1993).

However, the dates of the fourth or fifth century B.C. obtained from iron smelting furnaces at Taruga made them the earliest known in West Africa (Fagg, 1969; Tylecote, 1975) until the date of the 2nd Millennium BCE for Lejja iron smelting was produced (Okafor, 1990, Eze-Uzomaka, 2008). These dates, however, come before those for iron smelting in the “so-called” donor area, thereby refuting the argument that favoured the transfer of knowledge of iron smelting into West Africa from an external source. Contrary to that position, scholars like Davies (1966), Diop (1968), and Andah (1979, 1981), among others, argued in favour of an indigenous invention of the technology in West Africa. They argued that the diffusionist theory was very simple and lacked concrete evidence to support it. Andah (1979) and Diop (1968) further pointed out that iron smelting does not require very high temperatures (1100 C to 1300 C) and that the technique may have developed directly from pottery-firing techniques. Coghlan (1942), Shinnie (1967; 1971) and Tylecote (1975) argued in the contrary that the process of firing pottery was quite different from iron smelting which might not have provided enough firing temperature required for producing bloom as a result it would have been difficult for them to discovered the use of iron and mastered it without prior knowledge of copper and bronze metallurgy or rather without an external influence. However, the widespread occurrence of iron ore in both surface and underground deposits in West Africa may have been known to and exploited by the people for a long time (Okafor, 1992).

The third school of thought is the cautious group (Okafor, 1984, 1993, cited in Odofin, 2012). In this group are Andah (1979), Holl (1993), and Okafor (1993). Although they support the indigenous theory, they caution that further research is needed before reaching a conclusion, given ecological and technological diversity.

Iron Smelting on the Jos Plateau

Information on iron production on the Jos Plateau is scanty, and the few available sources were mostly documented by colonial anthropologists who merely recorded what they saw, and, until recently, by historians and archaeologists (Gubam, 2013; Maram, 2014). Some of the information also comes from legends, songs, and oral information (Meek, 1971). Anthropologists like Berthoud (1969), Gunn (1953), Netting (1968), Tambo (1976), and Temple (1963) reported that communities on the Jos Plateau had a high reputation as iron workers and further described the most common type of furnace used by these groups as “a pit covered in a pot-like shape with a hole in

it” (shaft furnace). Archaeological studies have also shown that the people of the area had good knowledge of iron smelting in antiquity and that this knowledge is related to the Nok civilization, which flourished between BC 200 and 1000 AD. Iron smelters in the two areas used similar furnace types (See Bulus et al., 2001; Gubam, 1995, 2013; Jemkur, 2004). Ropp Rock Shelter provided evidence of continuous occupation from the Late Stone Age to the Early Iron Age (York, 1965; Shaw, 1978), thereby revealing a transition from the Late Stone Age to the Iron Age. The presence of enormous iron smelting remains in the area further supports such claims. Berthoud (1969) also mentioned a different type of furnace which was observed at Ganawuri. His description shows that this furnace type is similar to the embedded furnace described by Jemkur (2004). Unlike the shaft furnace in which iron slag was emptied through the opening at the top, the slag from the embedded furnace was emptied through an opening at the base of the furnace.

Iron smelting in the Jos Plateau communities was not a specialized work like blacksmithing. It was carried out by anyone who could smelt iron, but only a few families were able to undertake the duties of smithing. It was the smiths who supplied iron tools to members of their communities and non-iron working villages. People could obtain the iron tools they needed only through trade (barter). Iron was purified by the blacksmith, who fashioned it into a range of tools such as hoes, spear points, arrow points, swords, knives, beads, bells for phonies, and ear and lip plugs, among others. The act of iron smelting was, however, seasonal and began after the harvest (Meek, 1971), and in most cases after the chief priest had carried out some rituals. Among the Ngas, the chief priest ceremonially cuts down the tree from which the charcoal subsequently used in smelting is obtained, after which all those who intend to smelt iron may then go out and cut the wood necessary for charcoal (Isichie, 1982). Recent studies have also revealed different practices involved in iron smelting by the Jos Plateau people (Jemkur & Walu, 2002; Gubam, 1995; Mangut and Mangut, 2017; Gubam, 2014; and Maram, 2014).

Figure 1: Iron Smelting and Iron Trade Areas on the Jos Plateau

Source: Modified from <https://www.openstreetmap.org/#map=6/9.117/8.674>
It is also evident from available records that the people had good knowledge of tin smelting, which was probably influenced by iron smelting, or vice versa (Freund, 1981). According to Taylor (1982) and Okpoko (1987, as cited in Odofin, 2012), the history of Tin mining and smelting in the area dates back to the fifth century B.C.

Plate 1: An iron smelting furnace at Nfwi
Source: Field Survey 2018

Plate 2: Heap of slags at Lai
Source: Field Survey 2018

Tin smelting was, however, not popular among the people, probably because its production was restricted to luxury goods, which could only be afforded by the privileged class in society. Various tin objects have been recovered from ancient iron-smelting sites in the area, suggesting that tin was used by local people to produce several objects, mostly ornamental. Information about tin smelting is scanty, probably because iron ore was readily available, and with iron ore, people could produce the objects they required and did not need to bother with using tin, which, although also available, was limited in quantity. Unlike iron smelting, which was opened to all, tin production was highly controlled because of its value. Slave labour was extensively employed for the exploitation of both iron and tin in the area (Freud, 1981; Lohor, 2011). Although the smelting processes for the two metals were similar, Cline (1937) maintained that tin has a lower melting point than iron. Remains of iron hoes were found 18 feet below the bed of the Dilimi River (Meek, 1971). In addition, iron bangles of different sizes were also found from a depth of 14 feet in the tin mines in Foron (Meek, 1971).

Plate 3: An iron smelting furnace at Nfwi

Iron material was highly regarded and played an important role in the social, political, and economic life of the people. Where iron ore was available, people produced iron beyond their own consumption, and the excess was sold to those in need, either within or beyond their immediate communities (Dakur, 2011; Lohor, 2011). Colonial masters acknowledged that the people had achieved so much in iron production and that the only means of overcoming them was disarmament. In 1904, a total of two hundred spears were seized at Hoss (in Riyom Local Government Area) alone, in spite of the clear deviance of the Hoss natives to surrender their arms to the British (Bukar, 1986). Similar measures were taken against the joint Mwaghavul force of Pushit, Panyam, Kerang, and Ampang West, although the number of iron implements collected during this encounter was not reported (Dazyam, 2005).

Plate 4: Short-handled hoes used for exchange and payment of bride price

Source: field survey 2023

Iron hoes were used as currency for the payment of bride price, as symbols of accumulated wealth, and in rituals (Isichie, 1982; Jemkur and Walu, 2002; Gubam, 2013). Among the Mwaghavul, Ngas, and Tarok, seven iron hoes could pay bride price. Among the Berom of Foron village and Buji, the iron hoe was later replaced by cowries as currency for the payment of bride wealth and the purchasing of goods. The situation was also similar among the ethnic groups on the lowland Plateau, particularly among the Goemai and the Kofyar, who later adopted cowrie shells as currency, thereby reducing the value of iron as a major means of exchange in the area. Iron bracelets were used for marriage engagement. The Mwaghavul bury their chief priest with an iron hoe (a practice similar to that of their Kanuri kinsmen), and only materials made from locally smelted iron are accepted for traditional purposes. Iron ore was common in the highland communities of Berom, Ron, Mwaghavul, Ngas, Kantana, Mupun, Buji, and Bache (Rukuba) and was exported to the lowland areas like Kofyar, Langtang, Azara, Wamba through different routes where it was traded further south among the Doemak, Kwalla, Jak of Namu, Taroh, Montol, Goemai, and far away Wamba, Nasarawa Eggon, Azara, and Awe in present-day Nassarawa state (Dakur, 2011, and Lohor, 2011). Salt and palm oil were collected in exchange. Even among the highland tribes, iron implements and iron also form important trade items.

Isechie (1982) reported that the Berom were skilled iron smelters and traded iron with the Ron, contrary to Alahira (2010), who asserted that the Ron obtained their iron from the Berom. Isechie's position was further confirmed by Maram (2014) and Gubam's fieldwork report (2021), which noted that the Ron were skilled iron smelters and traded only in iron with their Berom neighbours. The situation was also similar to that of other ethnic groups (Isichie, 1982; Jemkur and Walu, 2002). By the 18th century, the Jos Plateau communities were said to have exported iron wares to Hausaland through Bauchi and Lere (Lohor, 2010). In his words, "... the Mwaghavul were able to travel to Hausaland with their wares. They exported livestock, grains, iron, oil palm, and slaves to Hausaland in exchange for potash, spices, horses, and Hausa cloth" (pp. 165).

This position was asserted by Katu (2009), who states that iron and tin were the important items that attracted Hausa people from the north to the Jos Plateau highlands. Iron was therefore an important factor that promoted pre-colonial inter-group relations in the area. While, among most groups, iron was transported from mining sites to homesteads, where it was smelted by various families in the villages, the Ron restricted it to the mining sites such as Manguna, Karfa, Bargesh, Sha, and Mangar (Mangut and Mangut, 2017). The reasons for this are not yet established, but it is probably due to their proximity to ore and fuel sources.

The Jos Plateau iron smelters and blacksmiths obtain their fuel from common trees such as *gwaska* (in Hausa language), *malmo* (in Hausa language), *marke* (in Hausa language), *madachi* (in Hausa language), or *mahogany* (in English), *kanya* (in Hausa language), *pasagatari* (in Hausa language), *Baure* (in Hausa language). Each community selects the strongest tree species in its environment for charcoal production, but similar trees are exploited because they share common vegetation.

Comfort and life in the area generally revolved around iron. Blacksmiths were highly ritualized and associated with many myths. The blacksmiths play important role both in the installation of a new king as well as the burial of a king because it was the blacksmith that produced the important materials required for the installation like sacred spear, sacred iron chair, sacred hand bangles worn on the hand of the new king (*nkas ichin* in Bache language) and the sacred iron necklaces worn on the neck across the shoulder of the new king (*inyang inchin* in Bache language). Whenever a king died, the blacksmiths were expected to carry out some rituals before the corpse was buried. It was the blacksmith who led the new king into the shrine as well. The installation process only commences upon the blacksmith's arrival. Among the ethnic groups, iron bangles similar to that used for installation called were wore by young initiates two on both hands and another (the size of a big necklace or chain) was worn on the neck across the shoulder of the young initiate the initiation rite called *ichin* and *shaghal* (in Rukuba and Mwaghavul language respectively) which was usually performed annually (personal communication with Adankala, 2020). Four iron bracelets and the chain-like necklace were required by a young initiate. These materials were to be worn by an initiate for one or two months before the initiation rite and throughout the initiation period. Even after the initiation, the individual was expected to wear the bangles on sighting any danger (as a protective measure). After some time, those items were collected by the chief priest and kept in the shrine for another period of initiation.

Iron slag, on the other hand, was used for healing and the treatment of various ailments in the area. Iron bracelets were commonly used among the various ethnic groups for marriage engagements/proposal. This is called *bwot kim* (in Mupun language) and *lop kim* (in Mwaghavul language). A young man is expected to wear an iron bracelet on the left hand of his fiancée as a sign of engagement. Even in the present-day situation, where modern wedding engagements have taken over the local practice, the same name (*bwot kim and lop kim*) is used for the same purpose. Among the Buji people, iron bangles can also be worn by a couple once they have twins, as a way to protect them or to ward off ill intentions toward the twins (Personal communication with Mr. Danladi). This is against the backdrop of a common belief among the people that having twins is a sign of bad luck, so the couple must be protected against any ill intentions of the twins by

wearing the iron bangle. Various musical instruments used by the different groups on the Jos Plateau were made of iron. Some were tied around the legs of dancers, such as the ndol (in the Mwaghavul language), and were adorned by women.

In most parts of the northern Jos-Plateau area, especially among the Anaguta, Afizere (Jarawa), and the Ganawuri, knowledge of ancient iron smelting is fast disappearing from people's memories because of early contact with Europeans. Although no physical evidence was found, colonial records mention the presence of smelting furnaces in Ganawuri (Berthoud, 1969), which he described as different from those of the Berom and Angas ethnic groups. It is therefore possible that the long time between the periods of abandonment and the present might lead to memory loss and distortion. Another problem might be that the iron smelters in those places were professional smelters who kept the practice secret from other members of their communities, thereby leading to the distortion. The answer to this should be reserved for another research. In addition, the various groups on the Jos Plateau were famous for wearing various iron ornaments, such as bracelets, armlets, and leglets. Meek (1971) further affirmed that the Berom and Rukuba were known for wearing iron greaves. *Mak* or *Mwak* (in Aten language) was iron materials used for covering the nakedness of Aten women, which was produced by the Aten (Ganawuri) blacksmiths. It was also for adornment and the expression of wealth, as well as for personal communication, 2020. The shortage of fuel and the importation of ready-made iron scraps from Europe imposed serious constraints on the iron industries in Jos, Plateau State. The reduction in iron supplies during the Second World War affected many places (Meek, 1971), and to close the gap created by this unfortunate incident, many societies on the Jos Plateau were forced by colonial policy to revive traditional iron production (NAK/RPP/1192/196).

Colonial political economy of iron smelting in the Jos Plateau societies

The colonial political economy of iron production in the Jos Plateau societies can be better understood in the context of the decline of local industries, which is connected to deliberate colonial policies aimed at promoting the consumption of imported iron scraps from Europe. This is primarily aimed at impoverishing the people and also subjecting them to accepting the Western economic system without resistance (Bukar, 1986). To achieve this, the Europeans employed force to legitimize their actions, and violators and those unwilling to cooperate were made to face the wrath of colonial laws (NAK/DO/1076/22/1946). The first step was to destroy the iron-smelting industries in the area by cutting off the fuel supply (charcoal). The second step was the massive importation of scrap iron from Europe, as well as the regulation of its distribution. The third step was to ensure that these scrap irons were bought and that all taxes were paid in European currency, thereby shifting the youthful workforce required for iron smelting to the tin mines. The inferior iron scrap was forcefully imposed on the people. The decline of iron smelting in the area can be classified into the early phase and the later Phase; the early phase was the period when iron smelting in the Jos Plateau area was initially disrupted by the importation of iron pipe and scraps from Europe (before the Second World War (NAK/CCE/C.C.E7/130/387/1924). This period witnessed widespread theft of the materials by local people who could not afford to purchase them (NAK/SNP/898/1924/19/1924). Supplies of the materials were strictly controlled by the colonial government and the Nigerian railways. The shortage of iron in Europe,

occasioned by the outbreak of the Second World War, led to high demand for iron in the colonies and in Europe for the production of agricultural implements and weapons of war, respectively. To curtail the iron shortage during the war, colonial powers, including the British, directed their colonies to revive local iron-smelting industries (NAK/SNP/4246/1941).

The intention was to produce the material to meet local demand and for export. This was intended only to meet their demand during the war period, not to sustain local industry. The desire to revive local iron smelting this time was just to satisfy their capitalist desire to maintain productivity, not out of the love they have for local industries. Production of iron in Europe and its importation to the colonies was interrupted by the Second World War and they felt that the only way to provide iron for the production of farm implements in the colonies and maintain steady supply of iron for the production of armaments to prosecute the war was to revive/boost local production of iron in their colonies (NAK/DOP/1192/196/1941).

The second phase was the period after the Second World War, when people were tasked with reviving local iron-smelting industries. This marks the final phase of iron smelting abandonment in the Jos Plateau area (Fwatshak, 2005). This was facilitated by promoting European technological competition, which led to massive imports of scrap iron into Nigeria and the full implementation of the colonial tax system on local people (Goucher, 1981). In this case, the iron mining and smelting industries that had hitherto supplied the blacksmiths with the materials to work on were halted by the competition of cheaper and purer iron bars imported from Europe. This was boosted by the Industrial Revolution in Europe, which led to the proliferation of European iron goods in African markets, thereby increasing competition for African smiths. The impact and interaction of technologies have played an important role in this respect. With the imposition of the colonial tax system on the local population, the workforce needed to maintain local industries was diverted to the colonial tin mines. Hence, the traditional African iron-smelting industries were no longer able to meet the growing demand for iron, leaving people with no option but to accept the ready-made European iron bars available on the market. It is interesting to know that even after the introduction of the European iron bar, most communities on the Jos-Plateau were not ready to abandon local iron smelting because of the traditional demand for locally smelted iron, and secondly, the imported iron bar was perceived to be inferior in quality compared to the locally smelted iron. Although the importation of ready-made iron bars from Europe is an important factor, ecological and some human factors cannot be ruled out. Most tree species needed for charcoal production were gradually depleted or getting into extinction due to continuous deforestation, most of the able-bodied population needed for iron smelting was moving to the tin mines in order to get money to pay the heavy colonial tax (NAK/BPFC/162/14/36), and the laborious nature of local iron smelting was a contributory factor. Although local people have a strong preference for locally smelted iron, the consistent supply of scrap iron (NAK/NERC/C.C.E7/130/382/1924) made it attractive to them.

The enactment of colonial policies aimed at eradicating any form of competition with European industrial products was “the final straw that broke the camel’s back”. Laws were made to discourage the “indiscriminate” felling of trees. To achieve this, the

colonial administration formulated a policy that imposed severe petrol restrictions on lorry operators transporting firewood (NAK/CF/347/9/42). Another strategy is to provide a completely new substitute (importation of coal from Enugu), which will force the people to use coal as a substitute, and this was to commence in the mining field (NAK/RP/1236/67/42). This formed the basis for extending the Enugu rail line northward to the Jos-Plateau (NAK/RPP/G.M.1396/3296/42). To successfully implement such colonial policies, traditional rulers were involved.

However, the rate of theft in the minesfield increased since not everyone could afford to purchase the iron scrap (NAK/SNP/350/1919/10/24). The local people perceived the theft of scrap iron as a new and easy way to make money and were ready to do whatever it took to get away with it, selling it to others at lower prices. Although the indigenous population was not ready to work for the white men as labourers in the tin mines, they always hung around those mines for the slightest opportunity that came their way to steal from the white men's tin or iron scrap (Freund, 1981). Theft of scrap iron was carried out in different ways. The first method was the theft of keys, which, according to the colonial record, was the most common (see NAK/C.C.E.E/C.C.E7/130/382/1924), while the second method was to buy the iron scrap from the headman on the mines-field (NAK/RPP/5588/71/1945). The third method was to connive with the railway police, while the fourth method was through smuggling (NAK/NRM/512/A2/1924). Local iron smelting in the area finally ended in the mid-20th century (NAK/JOS/ PROF. 31/1915). However, this followed deliberate colonial policy against deforestation in the area leading to scarcity of fuel for iron smelting, the importation of European iron pipes and bars in the tin mine fields from Europe, mass movement and conscription of youthful populations to the tin mines, the deliberate effort of the colonial masters to eliminate all forms of competition to their industrial products all affected the progress of the industries (Fwatshak, 2005).

Conclusion

The nineteenth-century industrial revolution in Europe further stimulated colonial interest in Africa. The desire to expand political and economic influence beyond Europe led to the elimination of all forms of economic competition in the colonies, paving the way for the consumption of European goods. Different policies were formulated by the colonial administration in Nigeria to either directly or indirectly destroy local industries and the consumption of their products by the indigenous populations. In the Jos-Plateau societies, iron smelting was of particular interest to the colonial administration. The British have a lot of scrap iron that they want to dispose of, and the best place to do that is their colonies. Since people were more interested in locally smelted iron than in imported iron scraps because of its quality and traditional value, deliberate measures were necessary to enforce the abandonment of local iron smelting. Laws were enacted to ban the cutting down of trees by the people; a heavy colonial tax was imposed to force people to migrate to tin mines to earn money to pay it; among other measures, defaulters were made to face stiff penalties. A lot of politics was involved, such that the colonial economic policies were promoted at the detriment of the economic interests of the local people. There was a twist of events with the outbreak of the Second World War, as iron became a scarce material in Europe. This forced the British colonial administration in the Northern Province of Nigeria to revisit its economic policies by

revamping local iron-smelting industries in the Jos Plateau area for both local consumption and export. Strengthening colonial policies to eliminate iron-smelting industries in the area after the Second World War meant that these policies were intended to promote colonial economic interests.

References

- Andah, B. W. (1979). Iron Age beginning in West Africa: Reflections and Suggestions. *West African Journal of Archaeology* Vol. 9. Pp.135-150.
- Andah, B.W (1981). The band of Horeland project ethno archaeological investigation in path of the Benue valley Region, *West African Journal of Archaeology* 13, pp 23-60.
- Alahira, H. A. (2001). *The Role of Women in the Colonial Economy of Northern Nigeria: A Case Study of the Berom of Plateau 1900-1960*. Ph.D thesis submitted to the Department of History, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.
- Arkell, A. (1968). The valley of the Nile. In Oliver, R. (ed). *The Dawn of African History*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. 7-12.
- Avery, D. H., Merwe Van Der, N.J. and Scitowitz, S. (1988). The Metallurgy of Iron
- Berthoud G. (1969). Les Ganawuri du Nigeris. *Bulletin Annuel de' Ethnographic*, LXVI, 99-126.
- Bloomery in Africa. In R. Meald (ed.) *The Early Users of Metals and Alloys*. Cambridge. M. I. T. Press.
- Borok and Gubam, (2021). An Appraisal of the Absence of Inter-Marriage as one of the causes of conflict between Indigenes and Fulani herders in the Jos-Plateau rural communities: An ethno-historical analysis. *Conference Proceeding of the Ethnological and Anthropological Society of Nigeria*, Lokoja, 209-240.
- Bukar, D. (1986). *The mining and peasant improvement in Jos Division 1900-1950: A study in Colonial Domination and Underdevelopment*. Being an MA Dissertation submitted to the Department of History, Faculty of Arts and Social Sciences, ABU Zaria.
- Bulus, I, Goyol, A., Walu, L., Nengel, J. G., Bukar, D., Namang, S. Z. and Tenshak, D. (2001). *The Heritage and Hope*. Plateau State Government Publication, Jos.
- Cline, W. (1937). *Mining and Metallurgy in Negro in Negro Africa*. Menasha: Geogia Banta.
- Coghlan, H. H. (1977). *Notes on prehistoric and early iron in the Old World*. Revised edition. Oxford
- Dakur, M. (2011). Economic Structure: In Lohor, S.A., Katu, B.A., Lere, M. and Danfulani U. (eds.) *Towards A Mwaghavul History: An Exploration*. U.S.A Xlibris Corporation. PP. 132-147.
- Davidson, B. (1976). *African in History*. London. New York. Collier Books.

- Davies, O. (1966). *West Africa before the Europeans*. London
- Dakur, M. (2011). Economic Structure. In Lohor, S.A., Katu, B.A., Lere, M. and Danfulani U. (eds.) *Towards A Mwaghavul History: An Exploration*. U.S.A Xlibris Corporation. PP. 132-147.
- Dazyam, B. M. (2005). *So Mbarki: The Genesis of Modern Mwaghavul Society*. Jos. Kessy graphics Printers.
- Diop, L. (1968). Traditional iron working and the Iron Age in Africa. *Bulletin de l'IFAN (B)* 30:10-38
- Eze – Uzomaka, P.I. (2008). "Iron Age Archaeology in Lejja, Nigeria. In G. Pwiti, C. Radimilahy and S. Macano (Eds.), *Studies in the African Past*, Vol. 7, pp. 99-113.
- Fagg, B.E.B. (1959). The Nok Culture in Prehistory. *Journal of Historical Society of Nigeria*, 1(4), pp. 288-293.
- Fagg, B.E.B. (1969). Recent Work in West Africa: A New Light on the Nok Culture. *World Archaeology*, Vol. 1. PP. 41-50
- Freud, B. (1981). Capital and Labour in the Nigerian Tin Mines. London. Longman
- Fwatshak, S. U. (2005). Colonialism and indigenous enterprises on the Jos-Plateau. In G. Nengel (ed.), *Mangyeng Journal of Central Nigerian Studies*, A Publication of the Department of History and International Studies, University of Jos.
- Goucher, C. L. (1981). "Iron is iron" Till it is Rust: trade and Ecology in the Decline of West African Iron-Smelting. *Journal of African History*, vol. 22. No. 2, pp. 179-189.
- Gubam, D.S. (1995). *An archaeological Reconnaissance Survey of Dikut-Nyedung Iron Smelting Site in Mangu, Mangu Local Government Area of Plateau State, Nigeria*. Unpublished B.A. Project, ABU Zaria.
- Gubam, D.S. (2013). *An Archaeological Survey of Nfwi Abandoned Settlement in Mangu Local Government Area of Plateau State Nigeria*. Unpublished M. A. Dissertation A. B. U. Zaria.
- Gunn, H.D (1953). *Peoples of Plateau Area of Northern Nigeria*, London. International African Institute.
- Holl, A. F. C. (1993). Transition from Late Stone to Iron Age in the Sudano-Sahelian Zone: a case study from the PeriChadian Plain. In Thurstan Shaw, Paul Sinclair, Basseyy Andah and Alex Okpoko (eds). *The Archaeology o Africa: Food, Metals and Towns*. London, 130-143.
- Holl, A. F. C. (1997). Metallurgy, iron technology and African Late Holocene Societies. In R. Klein-Arendt (ed). *Traditionnelle E'senhandwerk in Africa*. Pp.13-54. Koln: Heinrich Bath Institut.
- Huard, P. (1966). The introduction and spread of iron to Chad. *Journal of African History* 7. 377-404.

- Isichei, E. (1982). *Studies in the History of Plateau State, Nigeria*. London. Macmillan.
- Jemkur, J.F. (1992). *Aspect of the Nok Culture*. Zaria. A.B.U. Press Ltd.
- Jemkur, J.F. (2004). The Beginnings of Iron Metallurgy in West Africa. In H. Bocoun (ed). *The origins of iron metallurgy in Africa: New light on its antiquity: West and Central Africa*. Paris. UNESCO 3-43.
- Jemkur, J. R. & Walu, I. D. (2002). Metallurgy and marriage in Tal area of Plateau State, Central Nigeria. A paper presented at an international conference on Theme, "Transition of Knowledge: Terracotta and Metals in West Africa and Cameroon organized by the French Institute of research in Africa at the Institute of African Studies, University of Ibadan, from 9th-13th September.
- Lane, P. (2005). Present to Past: Ethroarchaeology. In Tilley C.Y (ed), *Handbook of Material Culture*. PP. 402-425
- Katu, B. (2009). Pre-colonial History of the people of Jos Plateau. In I. O. Ojuade, Z. D. Goshit & G. J. Doki (eds). *Nigerian Peoples and Culture*. Ya Byang's Publishers, Abuja, Nigeria.
- Lhote, H. (1952). La Connassence du fer en Afrique occidental. Encyclopedie mensuelle d' Outre-Mer, 269-272.
- Lohor, A. (2011). Internal and External Relations. In Lohor, S.A., Katu, B.A., Lere, M. and Danfulani U. *Towards A Mwaghavul History: An Exploration*. U.S.A Xlibris Corporation. PP. 148-169.
- Mangut J. and Mangut, B. (2017). The Historical Archaeology of the Jos Plateau of Central Nigeria. an Overview. In N. Rupp, C. Beck & K. Peter (Eds.), *Winds of Change: Archaeological Contributions in Honour of Peter Bruinig*. Born. Dr. Rudolf Habelt GmbH. 275-284.
- Maram, M. M. (2014). *An Archaeological Study of Ancient Iron Working Sites in Mahurum, Bokkos L. G. A. Plateau State, Nigeria*. Being an Unpublished M. A. Thesis submitted to the Department of Archaeology, A.B.U. Zaria.
- Mauny, R. (1952). Essai sur histoire des metaux en Afrique accidentale. Bulletin de L'IFAN 14(2), 545-595.
- Meek, C.K. (1971). *Gazetteers or the Northern Province of Nigeria: Highland Chieftaincies*, Vol. IV. London. Frank Cass.
- Morrison. J. H. (1976). *Jos Plateau Societies: Internal changes and external influence*. Ph.D. Thesis submitted to University of Ibadan, Nigeria.
- Netting, R.M (1968). *Hill Farmers of Nigeria: Cultural Ecology of the Kofyar of Jos Plateau*. Washington. Settles and University of Washington Press.
- Odofin, K. T. (2012). Early Metal using Communities in Africa: West Africa. In A. I. Okpoko and A. L. Derefaka (eds.) *Archaeology and Early History of Africa*. Nsukka: University of Nigeria Press. 180-185.
- Okafor, I. G. (1975). Iron working and Iron workers among Awka Ibo. Unpublished paper, Centre for West African Studies, University of Birmingham.

- Okafor, E. E. (1992). Economy and Politics: factors of Technological Change in Nsukka Bloomery Iron Smelting. *Nigerian Heritage*, vol. 4
- Okafor, E.E (1993) "New evidence on early iron smelting south east Nigeria" In Thurstan shaw, Paul Sinclair, Basseyankeh, Alex Okpoko (eds). *The Archaeology of Africa: food, metal, and towns*. London. Routledge. 432-448.
- Okafor, E.E (1995) Early iron smelting in Africa: A review *West African Journal of Archaeology* 25(1), 83-102
- Phillipson D. (1985). *African Archaeology*. Cambridge. Cambridge University Press.
- Reid, D, M. A. (1994). "Symbolism and the social contexts of iron production in Karagwe." *World Archaeology*, 27: 144-161.
- Schmidt, P. R. and Avery, D. H. (1983). More evidence for an advanced prehistoric iron technology in Africa. *Journal of Field Archaeology* 10. 421-434.
- Shaw, T. (1978). An. Introduction to Archaeological Methods. *Lectures on Nigerian Prehistory and Archaeology*.
- Shinnie, P. L. (1967). *Meroe: A Civilian of the Sudan*. London
- Shinnie, P. L. (1971). *The African Iron Age*. Oxford
- Soper, R. (1971). Early Iron Age pottery type from east Africa: a comparative analysis. *Azonia* 6. 3-13.
- Sule, A. & Haour, A. (2014). The Archaeology of Northern Nigeria: trade, people and politics, 1500 BP onwards. *Azania: Archaeological Research in Africa*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/0067270x.2014.968330>. Routledge Taylor & Francis Group
- Sutton, J. E. G. (1976). Iron working around Zaria. *Zaria Archaeology Papers*, 8 and 12.
- Tambo, D. (1976). *Pre-colonial Iron-working on the Jos-Plateau*. Unpublished paper.
- Taylor, J. W. (1982). A Nigerian Tin Trade in Antiquity. *Oxford Journal of Archaeology*, Vol. 1(3), 311-324.
- Temple, C.L (1963). Notes on the Tribes, Provinces, Emirates and States of the Northern Provinces of Nigeria. London. Frank Cass and Co. Ltd.
- Tylecote, R. F. (1968). Iron smelting on the Nigerian Early Iron age site at Taruga, Abuja Emirate. *Historical Metallurgy* 2. 81-82.
- Tylecote, R.F (1975). The origin of iron smelting in Africa. *West African Journal of Archaeology* 5. 1-9.
- Tylecote, R. F. (1982). Metal working at Meroe, Sudan. *Meroitica* 6. 29-42.
- Van de Merwe, N. J. (1980). The advent of Iron in Africa. In T. S. Wertime and J. D. Muhly (eds). *The coming of the age of iron*. New Haven: Yale University Press. 463-506.
- Vondip, N. L. (2000). *Exploration in Tarok Culture*. Jos. Cross Road Communication.

Williams. D. (1969). African iron in the classical world. In L. Thompson and J. Ferguson (eds.) *Africa in Classical Antiquity*. Ibadan.

Williams. D. (1974). *Icon and Image*. London: Routledge.

York, R. N. (1965). Excavations at Dutsen Kogba, Plateau State. *West African Journal of Archaeology*, 8, 139-163.

Archival Sources

NAK/RPP/1192/196 Disposal of Scrap Metal

NAK/DO/1076/22/1946 Firewood cutting in Mangu and Gindiri Areas

NAK/CCE/C.C.E7/130/1924 Worn-out Picks and other Tools; Eastern Railway Constructions

NAK/SNP/898/1924/19/1924 Scrap Iron from Nigerian Railway-Purchases

NAK/SNP/4244/1941 Iron Smelting

NAK/DOP/1192/196/1941 Disposal of Scrap Metal

NAK/RPP/5588/71/1945 Scrap Metal

NAK/NRM/512/A2/1924 Restriction of cutting of trees

NAK/JOS/PROF.31/1915 Supply of scrap metal